

100 cm or more (3%). Rice cultivar CR314-5-10, developed at CRURRS, was identified as the most promising culture for the bunded uplands.

CR314-5-10 derived from IR42/IR5853-118-5, is a semidwarf culture with stiff straw and takes about 115 d to mature. It has good early vigor, allowing proper stand establishment and competition with weeds. It possesses a fair degree of tolerance for drought in the vegetative phase and has long panicles (27.5 cm). Grains are long and slender (length:width = 3.2) with white kernels; 1,000-grain weight is 24.0 g.

CR314-5-10 was evaluated under direct seeded conditions in station trials and under transplanted conditions in all India Coordinated trials from 1983 to 1985. In station trials it produced significantly higher average yields than check variety Ratna over a 2-yr period

Table 2. Performance of CR314-5-10 in multilocal trials under transplanted conditions, Bihar, India, 1983-85.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles (m ²)	Average yield ^a (t/ha)				
			Wet season		Dry season		
			1983 (20)	1984 (22)	1984 (6)	1985 (6)	
CR314-5-10	94	288	3.9	3.4	4.3	4.2	
Rasi	83	304	2.8	2.9	4.1	3.5	
IR36	94	320	3.6	3.2	4.4	4.0	
Increase (96)							
Over Rasi ^b					19		
Over IR36 ^b					4		

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the number of sites. ^bBased on mean of 4 seasons.

at Hazaribag and Kanke (Table 1). In the coordinated trials CR314-5-10 showed yield superiority to IR36 and Rasi (Table 2).

CR314-5-10 performed well under the lab-to-land program and was acceptable

to farmers. On the basis of its superiority in grain yield to the check varieties, coupled with its tolerance for drought and blast disease, it has the potential to replace Ratna and Rasi in the Chhotanagpur plateau. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination of rice

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Hydrocortisone, a steroid hormone of higher animals, promotes cellular activity by influencing carbohydrate and protein metabolism. We studied its effect on germination and growth of rice seedlings.

Seeds of IR50 were soaked in 0, 50, 100, 200, and 500 ppm concentrations of hydrocortisone solution for 6 or 24 h. Germination increased up to 100 ppm with 6 h soaking (see table). Soaking for 24 h improved germination more than 6 h soaking. Root and shoot lengths nearly doubled with 100 ppm hydrocortisone. Hydrocortisone may have promoted cell elongation or multiplication of cells, or both.

Dry matter accumulation decreased with hydrocortisone, probably because

Effect of hydrocortisone on germination and seedling growth. Coimbatore, India.

Hydrocortisone concentration (ppm)	Germination (%)		Root length (cm)		Shoot length (cm)		Seedling dry weight (mg)	
	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h	6 h	24 h
	0 (control)	60	80	7.13	7.06	3.79	3.07	16.08
50	70	85	7.87	8.28	4.22	3.29	15.25	14.94
100	80	85	14.29	13.76	8.07	7.33	14.90	15.00
200	60	85	6.42	7.89	3.39	3.08	15.25	15.70
500	65	70	6.21	5.85	3.55	2.34	15.23	17.00
CD	11	9	1.46	1.17	1.03	0.76	ns	1.54

of increased utilization of seed reserves. Higher maintenance respiration might also have contributed to lower dry matter accumulation.

Soaking in hydrocortisone for 24 h enhanced root growth but had a more adverse effect on shoot growth than soaking for 6 h. The 500 ppm concentration generally depressed germination and growth, perhaps because of the toxic effect of the chemical.

These findings suggest that hydrocortisone has the potential to increase cellular activities in plants.

Detailed studies on the effect of foliar hydrocortisone sprays at different growth stages on productivity are in progress. □

Genotype × planting system interaction for flowering in rice

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The number of days to flowering or